

CREATIVE SKILLS DEVELOPMENT CONTENT

Urinova Sabina Shuxrat qizi

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

Teacher of the "Music Education" department

urinovasabina26@gmail.com

+998 99 331 33 35

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Abstract. In this article, special attention is paid to scientific research on the content of creative skills, the development of innovative methods and electronic educational resources, and the identification of pedagogical opportunities aimed at organizing the process of developing the creative skills of future music teachers. Given

Keywords: music, creativity, competence, pedagogue, skill, education, upbringing, competence, creativity, communication, reflection, motivation, idea, hypothesis, information, initiative, curiosity.

A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific characteristics. Creativity is also reflected as an important factor of talent. In addition, creativity determines mental sharpness, "ensures active involvement of students in the educational process. Creative thinking can be clearly reflected in every social sphere. The teacher's creativity is reflected in his creative approach to the organization of professional activities organized by him. In recent years, this situation has been expressed by the concept of "pedagogical creativity". Pedagogical creativity is the ability of a pedagogue to create new ideas that serve to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process, as well as to positively solve existing pedagogical problems, unlike traditional pedagogical thinking.

The meaning of the concept of "creativity" is wider than the concept of "creative potential", "creative direction", because the phenomenon of creativity has a potential and active form. A creative person is a person who realizes his creativity in innovative achievements. Creativity is a component of creativity. The difference between the concepts of "creativity" and "creative orientation" is that the first one is related to intellectual development, while the second one is based on the type of activity that ensures the development of creative thinking.

- Creativity is focused on efficiency, creativity is the aspect of creativity based on motivational need;

- Creativity is a process characterized by the ability to express oneself in any type of activity, and creativity is a permanent personal characteristic;
- Creativity - constructive activity that creates innovations, creativity - the highest level of intellectual activity of thinking;
- Creativity - activity aimed at obtaining a new result, creativity - readiness to create new socially significant products of one's activity.

Based on the literature analysis, it can be understood that the psychological structure of creativity includes a system of creative parameters and is a unique combination of motivational, intellectual, aesthetic, existential, communicative parameters, as well as competence. The components of creativity determine the style of creative behavior and characterize productivity, innovation, having a unique way in the work process, a person's inclination and readiness for creative changes in various spheres of life.

Through creativity, the child not only learns real events and behavior in an artistic form, but also changes himself as a person with a certain social, moral and aesthetic attitude. The sequence of stages in the teacher's creative process can be structured as follows:

- the emergence of a pedagogical concept aimed at solving a pedagogical problem - concepts in solving the reality, methods, technologies, factors of the educational process that are considered a problem in their field;
- development of thought - after concepts appear in the process of thinking, thought develops in the analysis of pedagogical processes through necessary, unnecessary, necessary, unimportant, etc.;
- analysis, evaluation of the results of creativity and directing pedagogical tools to it - after a creative approach, the effectiveness is evaluated to a certain extent according to the analysis of its results and, accordingly, new ideas or existing tools are directed to the next creative process.

From the analysis of the above qualities, we can understand one concept, if we distinguish the areas of creative activity in which the future music teacher of the pedagogical university can show himself:

- methodological creativity - analysis of pedagogical situations, selection of models of professional behavior, design of the content and methods of pedagogical influence, study of advanced pedagogical experience and use of it, taking into account the individual characteristics of the teacher and students skillful application in practice;

- communicative creativity - the ability to choose areas of communication in professional activity and creative self-awareness, as well as the ability to control one's own activities;

- creative self-education - understanding the importance of creative development for one's professional activity, identifying professional and personal qualities that require further improvement, as well as developing a long-term program for self-improvement in the personal development system .

Creativity cannot be mastered by training, existing creativity can be developed. For this, "it is necessary to determine the characteristics of an individual person, to have the necessary skills, to face a problem, to create a special environment." Blindly memorizing and processing information does not lead to creative development, but rather, its creative transformation, finding a different meaning in it, a unique interpretation, forming a personal attitude to it, evaluating its importance, effectiveness, creative thinking and creativity leads to development. The future teacher's creative self-development determines the level of his professional development. This does not exclude creative development at all stages of the future teacher's professional training, on the contrary, creative development from the student will help to achieve the best results in the future professional activity.

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